

THE HEROISM OF SULTAN JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI

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Abstract. *In the Middle Ages, our great ancestors such as Sultan Jalaliddin, Sahibqiran Amir Temur and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur grew up among the righteous rulers and famous generals, who are the pride of our history and future. The life of the war, full of glory, is an epic of courage, and the eternal song of courage is a powerful motivation to realize the identity of our nation.*

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We should read and study the place of our great ancestor Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi not only in our country, but also in the whole Eastern world, as well as in world history, based on historical sources. If we consider that such historical figures are among the great ones who do not come in every century, their importance in educating the present and future generations in the spirit of military patriotism and loyalty to the country is incomparable. After all, Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi was an epic in languages for the freedom of his country, people, and freedom. Historical sources testify that there is a relative distance that cannot be compared to the second stage of the scale of the scale of the struggles, which cannot be compared to any past historical hero of the world, and historical justice continues to beat. Manguberdi's indomitable courage testifies to his future as an eternal icon for the entire world. He was born in 1199 as the first prince heir of Khorezmshah Muhammad Sultan. Only the first princess of Khorezmshah Muhammad, Aychechak, was from Khorezm, and all the other princesses belonged to his mother Turkon Khatun's Dashti Qipqoch warrior clan, tribes and court nobles. The children of princes born from them belonged to different nations from the same father and mother. The same thing was one of the main factors that ensured the beginning of disputes for the throne between the sons of princes Jaloliddin Manguberdi Pirshah, Uzlohshah, Rukniddin Gursantji, Akshah, who grew up in the court of Khorezmshah Muhammad. In fact, according to dynastic traditions, the eldest son, Prince Jaloliddin Manguberdi, was the rightful heir to the throne. He was also superior to other princes in terms of talent and potential. And Turkon Khotun not only used her great position in the palace, but abused it, excluding Prince Jaloliddin from the right of succession, while supporting her grandson Uzlohshah, who is considered her fellow countryman, with her whole body as the main claimant to the throne. , with this policy, he led the door of discord in the palace to the crisis of the kingdom. As a result, this dispute became one of the main factors that led to Genghis Khan's war against the Kingdom of Khorezmshahs and ensured his victories.

In fact, Jaloliddin Manguberdi was not only the eldest child of Muhammad Khorezmshah, but the Creator himself gave him all the qualities worthy of being an active participant in great events. Also, Prince Jaloliddin has a great teacher like Najmuddin Kubro, who took it upon himself to educate the famous people of the time, that is, to become a man of steel in the spiritual and spiritual sphere, as well as to protect him from all the horrors of the battlefield. He had teachers like Temur Malik and Shahabuddin Khawaqi, who were able to strike fear into the heart of his prey, who were capable of training him to become a warrior and a general. Especially, when

Sheikhul Valitarosh Najmuddin Kubro, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, demanded loyalty to the Motherland and its people even in difficult circumstances, and even though he lost his dear life and family, he fought for his holy land until his last breath on the battlefields. The fact that he inculcated such a sense of faith was important in his development as a selfless and patriot. It should be noted that the great teacher Najmiddin Kubro, although he died a sweet life if the country was oppressive, the idea of restoring it for its freedom based on the holy verses of the Qur'an, is a lesson in the Kubroviya sect of education and spirituality academy. had given For the first time in the world, when the enemy invades the country, first of all, men, women and men, all their spiritual, physical, religious and inner powers are embodied in the body like steel, turning it into a force of hatred against evil, and he created the idea of entering into battle. and he was a great person who was able to implement this practice. However, the Dashti Kipchak generals who were assigned to organize the defense of Old Urganch, before the main body of the Mongols arrived at the threshold of the capital, mounted a horse of treachery and treason, tried to kill the brave prince Jaloliddin, and a group of them gave his head to Genghis Khan. and the other part preferred to run away to places where dogs cannot find them. The short-sighted Jaloliddin Manguberdi's brothers, instead of fighting in the right and left of the battlefield under the protection of their brother, a talented military leader, brave man, instead of fighting in a line on the right and left of him, with the advice of Turkon Khatun, they took the front of the army and fell at Jaloliddin's feet. they were pierced with iron thorns. However, at this time, Sultan Jaloliddin, who was not able to fit in the capital, left Khorezm with a handful of loyal warriors, and in such precarious conditions, he decided to attract fifty hundred warriors in foreign countries to gather strength against the terrible army of Genghis Khan of three hundred and fifty thousand. At times when his hardships were crushing him like a mountain load, he traveled from region to region calling the people to a great holy war, riding night after night and day after day. The victories achieved by our above-mentioned great generals kept stabbing the heart of Genghis Khan, who was known as invincible, to the realization of his main goal of conquering the world. At first, Sultan Jaloliddin's mentor in the military field, Khojand Governor Temur Malik, fought six or seven times against Genghis Khan's large army during the defense of the fortress. Then the heroic defense of O'tror under the leadership of Inolchik Bahadir was added after all this trouble. It was still halwa. The bloodiest battles were about to begin, when Sultan Jaloliddin woke up like a lion and set fire to the field of battle to deliver crushing blows to Genghis Khan and his famous heroes. "We were born in this country, and we will die with honor for this country." "No one could deprive us of drinking the wine of martyrdom to the end of the Lord who created us." Genghis Khan dismissed this great man's answer as stubbornness. How does this great breed know how to get spiritual and spiritual nourishment and strength from the divine sciences of devotion to the country, patriotism, because Tobi, who grew up in the deserts and grew up with the breath of inhuman oppression and barbarism, is completely ignorant of the science of the school of science and madrasa. if The idea formed in his worldview is to control other peoples through the abominable means of slavery. It can be seen from this that Sultan Jaloliddin compared the flood of Noah's time to the second recurrence of the flood on humanity, and he strongly resisted the evil goal of Genghis and Genghis, which brought destruction and destruction. The only talented Sultan and army chief who exhausted my soul. Jaloliddin Manguberdi was able to defeat Genghis Khan and his generals, who did not know what defeat was in a battle with the generals of any country, near the banks of the Irgiz River and in the battles of Ghazna Valiyan, Bamiyan and Parvan. Genghis Khan was frightened by his victories.

China, Mongolian regions and East Turkestan repeatedly carried out mass mobilization and threw an insurmountable number of troops into battle against the small army of Sultan Jaloliddin. It was only because of this superiority that he was finally able to secure his victory. However, Genghis Khan admitted to Sultan Jalalid, who was his great admirer, who recognized his unparalleled military leadership. Because the unparalleled resistance of the Sultan did not allow the exhausted Genghis Khans to conquer the world. This was a great and unparalleled service of Sultan Jaloliddin to the people of the country. At this point, we find it necessary to refer to the works of the famous historians of the Middle Ages who praise the heroism of Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi. Mirzo Ulug'bek in his "History of Four Nations" quotes the following: "Sultan Jaloliddin wanted to fight in the field of valor, and following the trend of the times, he made the branch of the opposition a choice to be defeated." So that, like his father, he will not be a target for the blame of his people, and will not remain in the body of the artificial people of humanity. This situation was described by Mirza Ulug'bek in the above-mentioned work: "Genghis Khan gathered such an army here that the river was an arrow and the soldiers were a bow." Army joined army and blocked the way of Sultan's army. Sultan Jaloliddin bin Sultan Muhammad Khorezmshah saw himself between water and fire, on one side sharp swords were flaming, and on the other side a bloodthirsty, greedy river was screaming. There was absolutely no way out. Desperately entered the battle. Bravely, he put his horse into the battlefield, killed many of the Tatar infidels, and fought without any hesitation, so that if Rustami Dostan had been alive, he would have put the mantle of love for him on Jaloliddin's shoulders. If Kumushtan Isfandiyar had observed this battle, he would have willingly accepted the position of slave in his service.

No matter which direction the horse ran, it would stain the ground with blood. If Zol's son had seen this battle, he would have kissed Sultan Jaloliddin's hand." Genghis Khan, after watching Sultan Jaloliddin's battle and swimming across the river like a lion for a long time, turned to his sons standing next to him and said: "How happy is a father who has such sons!" He saved himself from the whirlwind of two calamities like water and fire and went to the beach. He still brings great calamities upon us. How can an intelligent person remain oblivious to him?" he said.

Look at the irony of fate that Sultan Jaloliddin was killed by a Kurd cursed, not in many devastating battles. Even the nature could not bear his death, so many young people cried and mourned, and even the birds on the place where he was killed, could not bear this terrible event and mourned. participants. In the words of An-Nasawi: "Indeed, this dirty, despicable person (Kurd) caused the greatest misfortune with his actions, leaving the world an orphan without Jaloliddin." An-Nasawi evaluated Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi as follows: "As for his bravery and courage, it is enough to remember his activities in battles." He was the best lion among lions, a fearless rider, the bravest among armies. He glorified righteousness and justice."

The conclusion is that Sultan Jaloliddin's struggle and life path is a symbol of bravery and courage, not only for the youth of our country and for our people, but also for humanity, which literally appreciates freedom and independence. His indefatigable and indomitable courage on the way to the independence of the Motherland is the most important benchmark of courage and the inspiration of bravery.

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